

Sleep Patterns in Parkinson's Disease: Insights from a Tertiary Care Center Using Polysomnography

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Abstract:

Introduction: Individuals with Parkinson's disease (PD) frequently suffer from sleep disturbance, which significantly hinders their quality of life and daily functionality.

Aim: This cross-sectional research explores sleep disorders among PD patients, analysing sleep parameters through polysomnography (PSG) and examining correlations with disease severity, staging, and duration.

Materials and Methods: A cohort of 52 PD patients from the neurology department of MGMGH underwent evaluations using standardized sleep scales, including the Parkinson's disease Sleep Scale (PDSS) and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS), in conjunction with PSG recordings.

Results: The study reveals a high prevalence of sleep issues, such as increased sleep latency, diminished sleep efficiency, REM sleep behaviour disorder, periodic limb movements, and obstructive sleep apnoea.

Conclusion: Sleep architecture is significantly impacted in PD patients. It is crucial that every Parkinson's disease patient undergoes a thorough assessment for sleep disorders to implement effective interventions enhancing their quality of life.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, polysomnography, sleep disorders, REM behaviour disorder, sleep efficiency, sleep latency.

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Introduction

Sleep, comprising about one-third of an individual's life, underpins crucial cognitive and physical functions essential for health. In Parkinson's disease (PD), sleep disturbances are highly prevalent, affecting 60% to 98% of patients and significantly contributing to non-motor symptoms [1]. These disturbances include difficulties in initiating sleep, nocturnal awakenings, early morning arousal, and excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) [2].

Patients may also experience vivid dreams, hallucinations, nightmares, panic attacks, periodic limb movements (PLMS) [3], restless leg syndrome (RLS), REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) [4], and respiratory issues like apnoea and hypopneas. These disruptions are linked to the degeneration of brain structures involved in sleep regulation, motor rigidity, depression, dysautonomia, and the effects of dopaminergic medications [5].

Evaluation typically involves a detailed clinical history and standardized sleep questionnaires, with polysomnography (PSG) and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale providing objective measurements.

Aim:

The purpose of this research is to examine the frequency and characteristics of sleep disturbances among patients diagnosed with Idiopathic Parkinson's Disease (PD). Furthermore, the study aims to evaluate sleep metrics using polysomnography and explore potential correlations between these metrics and key indicators of the disease, including its severity, progression, and scores from clinical assessments.

Materials and Methods

The study included 52 patients diagnosed with Idiopathic Parkinson's Disease (PD) based on the UK Parkinson's Disease Society Brain Bank Clinical Diagnostic Criteria. Subjects were recruited from both inpatient neurology wards and outpatient neurology clinics over a period of 7 months.

The study excluded bedridden individuals and those with coexisting conditions affecting sleep, such as unmanaged diabetes, cardiac insufficiency, COPD, dementia, or Parkinson-plus syndromes. Each subject underwent a thorough clinical evaluation,

including a detailed medical history and physical examination. The MDS-Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) was employed to assess disease severity. Sleep quality and daytime drowsiness were evaluated using the Parkinson's Disease Sleep Scale (PDSS) and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS), respectively. To objectively examine sleep patterns, polysomnography (PSG) was conducted.

Results

In a study of 52 patients, 36 individuals reported sleep-related issues. Among these, 31 had difficulty initiating sleep, while 25 struggled with sleep maintenance. Daytime drowsiness was reported by 16 patients. The study population consisted of 37 men (71%) and 15 women (29%), with ages ranging from 46 to 71 years and a mean age of 56.7 years. Disease duration varied from 1.5 to 13 years, averaging 6 years, with over half the patients (n=28)

falling in the 6-10 year range. Thirty-eight subjects were classified as Hoehn and Yahr stage 3 or lower, and 10 were at stage 4. Disease severity, measured by the UPDRS motor score, ranged from 11 to 41, with an average of 25.8.

A significant positive correlation was observed between disease severity and both disease duration and Hoehn and Yahr stages ($p < 0.05$). PDSS scores ranged from 90 to 140, with a mean of 125.90, showing a significant decrease as disease duration, severity, and staging progressed, indicating deteriorating sleep quality. Daytime sleepiness, evaluated using the ESS, was identified in 16 patients, particularly those with extended disease duration and higher severity and staging. ESS scores varied from zero to 16, averaging 6.26, with scores exceeding 10 considered abnormal.

Descriptive Statistical Data

Table 1: Subjective and Objective (Polysomnography) Results

	min	max	mean	S.D
Age(yr)	46	71	56.7	6.1
Duration(yr)	1.5	13	6	2.31
Staging	1	4	2.9	0.86
UPDRS motor severity	11	41	25.8	7.1
PDSS	90	140	125.9	23.02
ESS	0	16	6.26	5.1
Polysomnography				
TS Time (hour)	220	455	330	47.82
Latency (minutes)	8	58	29.3	11.45
Efficiency%	56	90	70.9	10
Maintenance%	52	99	73.82	11.26
REM episodes	1	3	2.12	0.479
PLMS	0	10	2.7	3.96
AHI	0	20	3.66	5.38

UPDRS - Unified Parkinson's disease rating scale; PDSS - Parkinson disease sleepiness scale; ESS - Epworth sleepiness scale; TS - Total sleep; PLMS - Periodic limb movement syndrome; AHI - Apnoea hypopnoea index

The polysomnography (PSG) results revealed significant sleep disruptions and associations with disease characteristics. Total Sleep Time (TST) ranged from 220 to 455 minutes, averaging 330 minutes. Reduced TST was observed in 75% of patients, showing a positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) with disease duration, stage, severity, and Parkinson's Disease Sleep Scale (PDSS) scores. Sleep Latency varied from 8 to 58 minutes, with a mean of 29.3 minutes, exceeding the normal 15-20 minute range in over half the patients. Sleep Efficiency, typically above 85%, ranged from 56% to 90%, averaging 70.9%, with only 13 patients achieving normal efficiency. The study found a significant increase in NREM sleep stages N1 and N2, and a decrease in slow-wave sleep (N3) in 80% of patients ($p < 0.05$). REM sleep duration was generally reduced, with varying numbers of REM episodes across patients. REM sleep onset latency

was extended in 76% of patients. REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) was identified in 21% of patients but showed no correlation with disease parameters or sleep scores. Periodic Limb Movements during Sleep (PLMS) were detected in 16 patients, with the PLMS index strongly correlating ($p < 0.005$) with disease characteristics and sleep scores. Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS) was diagnosed in 21% of patients, all of whom also experienced PLMS. RLS showed significant associations with disease duration, severity, and staging. Sleep Disordered Breathing (SDB) was assessed using the Apnoea-Hypopnea Index (AHI), with scores ranging from 0 to 20 (average 3.66), showing no significant correlation with disease parameters ($p > 0.05$). Snoring was reported in 15 patients, correlating significantly with Epworth sleepiness and PDSS scores ($p < 0.05$). This examination underscores common sleep disorders

including decreased TST, extended latency, reduced sleep efficiency, modified NREM and REM sleep patterns, RBD, PLMS, RLS, and mild SDB, as well

as their relationships to disease progression and sleep metrics.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Analysis (N=52)

	Duration (r, p-value)	Staging (r, p-value)	Severity (r, p-value)
PDSS	-0.821, <0.05	-0.821, <0.05	-0.952, <0.05
ESS	-0.844, <0.05	-0.835, <0.05	-0.827, <0.05
TST	-0.761, <0.05	-0.744, <0.05	-0.747, <0.05
SL.MAINTENANCE	-0.845, <0.05	-0.846, <0.05	-0.97, <0.05
SL.EFFICIENCY	-0.783, <0.05	-0.843, <0.05	-0.752, <0.05
SL.LATENCY	-0.834, <0.05	-0.853, <0.05	-0.90, <0.05
PLMS	-0.556, <0.05	-0.645, <0.05	-0.505, <0.05
AHI	0.042, >0.05	0.164, >0.05	0.220, >0.05

UPDRS - Unified Parkinson's disease rating scale; PDSS - Parkinson disease sleepiness scale; ESS - Epworth sleepiness scale; TS - Total sleep; PLMS - Periodic limb movement syndrome; AHI - Apnoea hypopnoea index

Discussion

The research evaluated sleep disturbances in individuals with PD using the PDSS and ESS, with an ESS score above 10 considered notable. Results revealed that 75% of subjects experienced diminished sleep quality, while 30% noted excessive daytime drowsiness. This differs from Verbaan et al.'s study, which observed a higher incidence of daytime sleepiness (43% of PD patients) compared to night time disruptions [6]. Both PDSS and ESS scores showed positive associations with disease longevity, stage, and intensity ($p < 0.05$), aligning with Kumar et al. and Cano-de-la-Cuerda et al.'s observations of a link between PD advancement and increased sleep issues [7,8].

TST was diminished in 75% of subjects (39 individuals), spanning from 220 minutes (3h 40min) to 455 minutes (7h 35min). A strong negative correlation was observed with disease duration, severity, and staging. These findings concur with Diederich NJ and Dhawan et al., who reported similar decreases in TST and sleep efficiency as PD progressed [9,10]. Sleep Latency was prolonged in 52% of patients (27 individuals), with the longest latency at 58 minutes and a mean of 29.3 minutes, exceeding that of healthy elderly individuals who typically fall asleep within 20 minutes. Investigations by Kaynak et al. and Wetter et al. found comparable extensions in sleep latency, averaging 30.7 and 32.6 minutes, respectively [11,12].

Sleep Efficiency dropped below the normal threshold (85%) in 76% of patients (39 individuals), with only 13 achieving standard readings. This reduction surpasses findings from earlier studies, such as yong et al., who reported an efficiency of 59.4 ± 22.0 , suggesting that PD patients experience substantially lower sleep efficiency compared to healthy controls [13]. The research uncovered altered Sleep Architecture in 80% of subjects (41 people), characterized by an increase in lighter sleep

phases (N1 and N2) and a reduction in deep and REM sleep, validating the significant effect of Parkinson's Disease (PD) on sleep patterns. These outcomes are consistent with earlier investigations by González-Naranjo et al. [14]. Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) was detected in 21% of subjects (11 people), showing no association with disease metrics. This differs from Sixel-Döring et al.'s research [15], which noted a higher RBD prevalence (86.9%) suggesting variability in RBD manifestations across different groups.

Periodic Limb Movements in Sleep (PLMS), a notable non-motor impairment in PD that disrupts sleep, was identified in 30% of subjects (16 people). The PLMS index, which quantifies hourly events with scores above 5 considered abnormal, yielded results higher than with findings by Yong et al. (mean PLMS index of 10.3 ± 18.1) [13]. PLMS exhibited strong associations with PD staging, severity, duration, and sleep scores, leading to frequent nocturnal awakenings and disturbed sleep.

In this study, Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS) was identified in 11 patients (21%), all of whom also displayed Periodic Limb Movements in Sleep (PLMS). Extended sleep onset was observed in nine RLS patients, and RLS exhibited notable associations with disease longevity, intensity, and sleep metrics. The RLS prevalence observed aligns with Xianchao Zhao et al.'s research [16], which noted RLS in 28% of Parkinson's disease (PD) patients, double the rate found in the general population.

Sleep-Disordered Breathing (SDB), characterized by apnoea and hypopneas and measured by the Apnoea-Hypopnea Index (AHI), was detected in 42% of patients (22 out of 52) with AHI > 5 . However, AHI scores showed no correlation with disease parameters, contradicting Arnulf et al.'s findings of a positive link between AHI and PD progression [17]. Snoring, quantified by the snore

index, was present in 28% of patients (15 individuals) and demonstrated significant correlations with the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) and Parkinson's disease Sleep Scale (PDSS) scores. This snoring is likely attributed to compromised upper airway function in PD.

The research underscores the influence of PLMS, RLS, and SDB on sleep quality in PD, highlighting their relationship with disease severity and progression. It reveals a strong link between PD advancement and deteriorating sleep patterns, with sleep quality declining as disease intensity and disability increase. This challenges earlier studies suggesting different rates of decline in sleep and motor centres. The results indicate that most sleep parameters significantly correlate with disease severity, suggesting concurrent effects on both centers, albeit at varying rates.

Conclusion:

Sleep disorders are common among individuals with Idiopathic Parkinson's Disease. Total sleep time significantly decreases as disease severity, stage, and duration increase. Patients experience a reduction in slow-wave sleep (N3) and an increase in lighter sleep stages (N1/N2), along with decreased REM sleep duration. REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) occurs in 20% of patients without a clear correlation to disease parameters. Extended sleep onset and reduced sleep efficiency, due to frequent awakenings, further contribute to sleep fragmentation, compounded by periodic limb movements, restless leg syndrome, and obstructive sleep apnoea, which negatively impact daytime functioning. Consequently, it is essential for all Parkinson's patients to undergo evaluation for sleep disorders to facilitate timely interventions aimed at improving sleep quality.

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